

EFFECT OF COMPOST PRODUCTION ON SOIL WATER AND NUTRIENT DYNAMICS IN CLAY LOAM SOIL

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Keywords

*Effect;
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Abstract: *This research was carried out to check the effect of compost on the water content and soil properties. Four composts from different feedstock was applied at 2.5-cm thick mulch layer to Clay Loam Soils and their effect on soil properties was studied after 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 weeks in which the pots were kept outside. The compost treatments were C1 and C2 (from organic fraction of municipal solid waste); C3 (from kitchen waste and animal manure); C4 (from straw and chicken manure). Control I (C1) is a soil without compost as amendment. At each sampling date, the soil was collected after removing the compost mulch. The coarse-textured compost (C2) had the least effect on nutrient availability despite moderate concentrations of available N and P in the compost. The total N and P concentrations were low which, together with the coarse texture of the soil resulted in low mobilization rates. The other three composts increased aggregate stability and water holding capacity although there was no measurable increase in soil organic, C, suggesting that the improved soil structure may be due to microbial activity. The soil N and P availability was increased by these three composts. The increased soil nutrient availability was due to two mechanisms which varied with compost type: either by release of P and N already present in available form in the composts, or mobilization of the nutrients during the experiment. However, the mobilization rate varied with compost type.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, organic matter is increasingly being ploughed back as soil amendment. The incorporation of organic manure into soil prolongs productive life of the soil and influences other properties such as soil structure, water

holding capacity and water movement. Organic matter tremendously improves soil physical properties and ameliorates the effect of acidifying inorganic fertilizer under continuous cultivation.

The economics of organic manure use in crop

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production becomes a challenge because of the high nutrient demand. Organic manure used in crop production not only maintains the soil quality but enhances yield, with minimum cost of procurement depending on sources. During composting, organic compounds are transformed into more stable and complex organic matter via humification (Lee et al. 2009). The rate and extent of these transformations may depend on the nature of the starting materials and composting conditions. During composting, the organic matter initially undergoes a rapid decomposition but later, during humification the compounds predominate (Kawasaki et al. 2008). The reduced ability to use traditional soil fertility management practices such as fallow and crop rotation to restore soil fertility limit farmers' productivity. Organic manure remains the major natural and sustainable means of rectifying soil fertility. Biodegradable waste if well managed could be of immense help in ameliorating soil nutrient problem. The study is aimed at analyzing the effect of compost on soil water and nutrient dynamics.

Moisture is an important environmental factor affecting microbial activity and therefore temperature and composting rate. According to Tequila et al. (2008), a moisture content of 50-65% is generally considered optimal for composting. Too little moisture (<30%) inhibits bacterial activity whereas high moisture content

(>65%) results in a slow decomposition, anaerobic conditions, bad odour and nutrient leaching.

Temperature is also one of the key factors affecting the composting process. Compost heat is produced as a by-product of microbial breakdown of organic matter (Nakasaka et al. 2005). The heat production depends on the size of the pile, its moisture content, aeration, and the C/N ratio of starting materials. The temperature change during composting is mainly divided into two distinct phases of, namely mesophilic phase (<45°C) and thermophilic phase (>45°C). A rise of temperature during thermophilic stage leads to pasteurization of pathogenic microorganisms in the materials, promotion of water evaporation from the composting solid materials, and acceleration of the rate of decomposition of organic matter in the composting materials (Margesin et al., 2006; Nakasaka et al., 2005). However, if the temperature during the thermophilic phase is higher than 70°C, microbial activity will be inhibited which can negatively influence compost quality or maturity (Lynch et al. 2005; Margesin et al. 2006). The temperature decreased to ambient when the compost was mature.

The activity of a number of enzymes such as dehydrogenase, urease, beta-glucosidase, phosphatase and arylsulphatase is high in the

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initial phase of composting and decreases over time (Castaldi et al. 2008). Changes in substrate composition will lead to shifts of microbial populations which are responsible for producing specific enzymes breaking down different substances at different composting stages (Albrecht et al. 2010; Jarvis et al. 2009).

During the composting process, respiration rates are initially high, but decrease with composting time as dissolved organic C (DOC) concentrations decrease (Abid et al. 2007). Compost is considered mature and stable when the respiration rate is less than 5mg CO₂-C g compost⁻¹ day⁻¹ (Said-Pullicino and Gigliotti, 2007). Changes in chemical and physical properties of the compost result in shifts in the activity and composition of microorganisms in the compost, with mesophilic microorganisms (mesophiles) dominating in the initial and final phases, whereas thermophilic microorganisms (thermophiles) dominate in the middle phase when the temperature is high (Amir et al. 2008). Bacteria dominate in the early stages of composting because they are generally more competitive than fungi and actinomycetes in the presence of easily-degradable compounds (Ryckeboer et al. 2003). As the relative concentration of aromatic and recalcitrant compounds in the remaining material increase it becomes dominant because many bacteria lack the specialized enzymes required to break down

and utilize aromatic compounds (Amir et al., 2008).

Composts have several advantages compared to plant residues when applied to soils, such as reduced volume, slower mineralization rates and recycling of municipal bio-solid wastes. Compost has two main effects on soils, particularly nutrient-poor soils: replenish soil organic matter and supply plant nutrients (Sanchez-Montero et al. 2004). Organic matter plays a crucial role in improving physical, chemical and biological properties of soils. Soil structure can be improved by the binding between soil organic matter and clay particles via calcium bridges and through stimulation of microbial activity and root growth (Farrell and Jones, 2009). Organic matter can indirectly improve soil structure by increasing microbial activity and thus production of microbial slimes, fungal hyphae and/or roots bind aggregates together. Organic matter is a significant reservoir of nutrients and can retain nutrients in a plant-available form (Baldock, 2007).

Other beneficial effects of composts include increasing water holding capacity and plant water availability (Curtis and Claassen, 2005; Farrell and Jones, 2009), decreasing leaching of nutrients (Hepperly et al. 2009), reducing erosion and evaporation and prevention of plant diseases. Further, compost can act as a long-term slow release fertilizer. However, the application of

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immature compost can have negative effects on plant growth due to its unpleasant or nuisance odor production, potential to inhibit plant growth and reduce N availability in the soil. The beneficial effects of compost are only achieved when mature compost is added to the soil.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The soil used for the study was a Brown Earth Soil (Clay Loam). The top 0-10 cm soil was collected, air-dried and sieved to <5 mm. Soil particle size distribution was analyzed using the Bouyoucos hydrometer method which relies on the Stokes's law. The soil was wetted to 65% field capacity and the composts were applied as a 2.5 cm layer on the soil surface corresponding to 122, 100, 127 and 110g moist compost for C1 to C4. Previous studies (Mat Hassan *et al.* 2011; Setia *et al.* 2011) had shown that soil respiration and plant growth were maximal at this water content in a soil of this texture. In this study, the following five treatments (with 4 replicates per sampling date) were set up with four types of composts applied as mulch, namely: C1 and C2 (from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste); C3 (from animal manure) and C4 (from straw and animal manure).

The 1-kg pots were kept outdoors. During this time, they received water only from the natural precipitation. Holes were made in the bottom of the pots to allow for drainage and prevention of water saturation. The pots were respectively

sampled at 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 weeks after compost application for determination of the properties listed below. At each sampling date, the compost layer was removed, only the soil was analyzed for the properties.

Soil and compost pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were measured in a 1:2.5 soil/water suspension (w/v) after 1 hr shaking at 25°C. The EC is a measure of the concentration of soluble salts in a solution with 1 dS/m being equivalent to 585 mg NaCl. Field capacity was measured using a pressure plate connected to a 100-cm water column (Pm=10 kPa) (Klute 2006). Total N and P were determined as described below for the plant material. Inorganic N (NH₄⁺-N and NO₃-N) was extracted with 2M KCl at a 1:10 dry soil/solution ratio with 1hr shaking. Ammonium-N was measured by the nitroprusside/dichloro-S-triazine modification (Blakemore *et al.* 2009) of the Berthelot indophenol reaction at the wavelength of 650 nm. Nitrate-N was measured by the cadmium reduction method.

Available P was extracted from 2g of freeze-dried soil with anion exchange resin membranes following K; the P concentration was measured calorimetrically as described by Murphy and Riley (2002). Total organic C (TOC) was measured using wet digestion with sulphuric acid and an aqueous dichromate mixture; the digests were back-titrated for the residual potassium dichromate with ferrous sulphate

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(Walkley and Black 2004). Soil aggregate size distribution were measured using a modification of the wet-sieving method of Cambardella and Elliott (2004) in which 32 g of air dried soil was sieved to 5 mm and then wet-sieved for 3 minutes on a nest of four stacked sieves in the order 2000µm, 1000µm, 500µm and 250µm in RO water vertically at an amplitude of 3 cm at 25 cycles per minute. The water-stable aggregates were then grouped into >1 and <1 mm size class. For dissolved organic C (DOC), 5 g of freeze-dried soil were shaken with 25 mL distilled water (1:2.5 w/v soil: solution ratio) for 60 minutes at a speed of 200 rpm. The soil extracts were then centrifuged at 28,200 Xg for 10 minutes and the supernatant vacuum-filtered and stored at -20°C until analysis. The C concentrations in the extracts were measured by titrating 4 mL of extract against 33 mMole ferrous ammonium sulphate hexahydrate after adding 1.0 mL 66.7 mMole potassium dichromate and 3-4 drops o-phenanthroline monohydrate indicator solution.

Results and Discussion

The results of the soil analysis as shown in the control column in Table 1 reveals the following properties: textural class: Clay loam, pH (1:2.5 soil/water): 5.83, EC: 0.15dS/m, available P: 40.70 mg/kg, Total P: 0.45mg/kg; Total organic C: 10.50 mg/ kg, dissolved organic C: 1.42 mg/kg, available N: 12.05 mg/kg; Total N: 1.51mg/kg; bulk density: 1.45g/cm³, and water-holding capacity (WHC): 0.25mg/kg.

The four composts labeled C₁, C₂, C₃, and C₄ in Table 1 differed in a range of properties. Compost 1 was fine textured and had the highest concentration of total N (16.45mg/kg) and dissolved organic C (34.30 mg/kg). Compost 2 was coarse-textured and had the highest total organic C (30.70 mg/kg) and with the lowest pH (5.60). The EC was highest in C₃ (6.92dS m⁻²) which was coarse-textured and had high concentrations of available N (136.23mg/kg) and total P (4.20mg/kg). Compost 4 was medium-textured and had the highest concentration of available P (11.42mg/kg), pH (7.90), water content (0.74mg), but with the lowest EC (0.7dS/m²).

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of the four composts (C1, C2, C3, C4 and Control)

	Unit	C1	C2	C3	C4	Control
pH		7.80	5.60	6.40	7.90	5.83
EC	dS/m ²	3.90	1.24	6.92	0.78	0.15
Bulk density	g /cm ³	0.49	0.93	0.49	0.36	1.45
Water content	mg/kg	0.42	0.52	0.38	0.74	0.25
Resin P	mg/ kg	9.20	17.30	4.50	352.30	0.45
Available P	mg /kg	2.05	0.46	4.20	11.42	40.70
TOC	mg/kg	16.10	30.70	12.30	29.90	10.50
Available N	mg/ kg	8.80	90.80	136.23	29.61	12.05
Total N	mg/kg	16.45	7.10	8.70	10.00	1.51
Dissolved organic C	mg/ kg	34.30	15.30	28.03	28.41	1.42
Particle size						
4.75-3.25 mm	%	36.50	36.50	36.50	36.50	36.50
2-1 mm	%	20.20	20.20	20.20	20.20	20.20
0.5-0.25 mm	%	43.30	43.30	43.30	43.30	43.30
Texture						CL

C1, C2, C3, and C4 = Treatments (Composts), CL = Clay loam

From 16 weeks onwards, the field capacity in the soil amended with C1, C3 and C4 was significantly higher than in the soil amended with C2 and the un-amended soil. Water-stable aggregates were determined only at the end of the experiment, 24 weeks after compost application (**Fig. 1**). The proportion of aggregates > 1 mm was greater in the soils amended with C1, C3 and C4 than in the soil amended with C2 and the un-amended soil. The

soil pH did not change significantly over time and varied from 5.60 to 7.90. At the end of the experiment (24 weeks), the soil pH was higher in the soils amended with C1, C2 and C4 than in the un-amended soil and the soil amended with C3, with greatest increase with C1. The EC was increased by the addition of C1, C3 and C4 compared to C2 and the un-amended soil, and did not change over time (**Table 2**). The total organic C concentration was not affected by compost addition or compost type and did not change significantly over time, except in the soil

amended with C2 after 24 weeks where the total organic C concentration was significantly lower (about 45%) than in the other treatments. The dissolved organic C concentration did not change significantly over time but was significantly higher than the un-amended soil in the soil

amended with C2 after 12 weeks and in the soil amended with C4 after 12, 16 and 20 weeks..

Table 2: Soil dissolved organic C (mg/kg) with no compost or amended with four different composts (C1, C2, C3 and C4) over 24 weeks (n=4).

Dissolved organic C (mg kg⁻¹)

Sampling dates (Weeks)	Treatments				
	C1	C2	C3	C4	Un-amended soil
4	2.95	1.19	1.41	2.41	1.81
8	2.48	1.33	2.86	2.38	1.68
12	2.62	2.83	1.63	2.94	1.29
16	2.13	1.23	1.33	2.45	1.32
20	2.62	1.66	2.62	2.74	0.84
24	1.34	1.21	1.43	2.12	1.45
LSD.			0.64		

Figure 1

Fig. 1: Water-stable aggregates >1 mm and <1mm after 24 weeks in soil without compost or amended with four different composts (C1, C2, C3 and C4). * indicates significant difference from the un-amended soil.

The available P concentration significantly increased over time in the soils amended with C1, C3 and C4, but not in the un-amended soil

and the soil amended with C2 (Fig. 2). Compared to the un-amended soil, the available P concentration was always higher in the soils amended with C3 and C4, whereas from 20 weeks onwards, it was lower in the soil amended with C2 with differences becoming more evident over time. When compared to the un-amended soil, application of C1 and C3 increased the concentration of available N 1-2-fold from 8

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weeks onwards (**Fig.3**). Compost 4 did not affect available N concentration in the first 12 weeks but then increased it to concentrations similar to

those of C1 and C3. Compost 2 had no effect on available N concentrations compared to the un-amended soil.

Fig. 2: A graph of soil available P (mg/kg) against weeks after calculating the LSD (n =4)

Fig. 3: A graph of soil available N (mg/kg) against weeks after calculating the LSD (n=4)

This study showed that composts differed in their effect on soil properties in the bioassay and that this effect changed over time. The coarse-textured compost had the least effect on soil properties and plant growth. Application of the other composts resulted in increased N and P availability, but this was due to different processes: release of N and P already present in available form in the compost at the time of application or mobilization of N and P during the course of the study.

Compost application had little effect on total and dissolved organic C, pH and EC in the soil (Table 2). This may be due to the application method as the composts were added as mulch. No compost application had little effect on total and dissolved organic C, pH and EC in the soil. This may be due to the application method as the composts were added as mulch, not incorporated. Furthermore, rainfall would have leached dissolved salts and possibly even particulate organic matter from the pots. The increase in soil pH by C1, C2 and C4 could be due to ammonification of compost-derived N and the presence of Ca and Mg in the composts which may have released H⁺ from exchange site and subsequent leaching of

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protons. The aggregate stability increased in C1, C3 and C4 (Table 1), but not in C2, although the total organic C concentration was not different from the un-amended soil. The increased aggregate stability and thus improved soil structure and water-holding capacity is suspected to be most likely due to microbial activity which was stimulated by the nutrients leached from the composts because bacterial slimes and fungal hyphae improves soil aggregation.

Composts 3 and 4 resulted in the highest concentrations of available P. However, the processes leading to the high P availability differed between the two composts. In C4, the high soil P availability can be explained as the high P availability in the compost at the time of application. On the other hand, P availability was low in C3. However, the C3 compost was characterized by a high total P concentration. Thus, P was mobilized during the experiment in this compost. Compost C1 also had a high total P concentration but did not increase P availability, suggesting that little P was mineralized from this compost during the course of the experiment. The P immobilization with C2 can be explained by its low total P concentration (Table 1). The available N concentration was increased by C1, C3 and C4. With application of C1 and C3, the increase in available N was very rapid whereas it

was slower with C4. With C3, the rapid increase in available N can be explained by its high concentration of available N at the time of application. However, the available N concentration was low in C1, suggesting that N was rapidly mineralized in this compost after adding it to the soil. The increase in available N concentration in the soil was slower with C4 which had moderate concentrations of available and total N.

Conclusion

This study shows that the effect of composts applied as mulch on soil nutrient availability varies with time and compost type. Coarse-textured composts with low total N and P have little effect on soil properties, even 24 weeks after application. With the medium and fine textured composts, N and P availability increased over time. The effects of the composts on nutrient availability is a function of two mechanisms: (i) N and P already present in the compost in available forms leaching into the underlying soil, and (ii) mobilization of N and P in the compost over time with the rate of mobilization varying with compost type. This study therefore, highlights the importance of compost particle size on nutrient release. Finer-textured composts have a greater surface area-to-volume ratio which increases decomposition rate and also aids leaching of nutrients.

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